
Making Social Innovators - Novel Innovation Education for Youth in Makerspaces

Eva-Maria Hollauf*

Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH, Jakob-Haringer-Str. 5/3, 5020
Salzburg, Austria. E-mail: eva.hollauf@salzburgresearch.at

Veronika Hornung-Prähauser

Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH, Jakob-Haringer-Str. 5/3, 5020
Salzburg, Austria. E-mail: veronika.hornung@salzburgresearch.at

Daria Podmetina

Lappeenranta University of Technology, P.O.Box 20, FI-53851, Lappeenranta,
Finland. E-mail: daria.podmetina@lut.fi

Elisabeth Unterfrauner

Centre for Social Innovation, Linke Wienzeile 246, 1150 Vienna, Austria.
E-mail: unterfrauner@zsi.at

Guntram Geser

Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH, Jakob-Haringer-Str. 5/3, 5020
Salzburg, Austria. E-mail: guntram.geser@salzburgresearch.at

* Corresponding author

Abstract: This contribution deals with the results of a scientific evaluation of a new way of coaching young learners in social innovation projects in makerspaces. The approach aims at fostering an entrepreneurial mindset, creativity and maker skills needed to design and visualise a prototype in the course of a social innovation project. Moreover, they acquire digital literacy skills needed to share innovative ideas solving societal issues. The approach was trialled in more than ten European countries with 1.002 children.

Firstly, we will describe the theoretical background and didactical facets of the programme. Secondly, we illustrate practical examples of the large scale pilot run in and out-side school in fablabs or mobile makerspaces in schools. Thirdly, we present the scientific findings of skill acquisition, especially the parameters of self-efficacy and creativity. The final section discusses the results, adaptations and further outlook of the new programme.

Keywords: social innovation; entrepreneurial learning; sustainable development goals for young learners; prototyping with maker tools; makerspace;

1 Introduction

Today's society requires new social entrepreneurial and innovation skills and competences to meet uprising global challenges (Makhlouf, 2011). The question of how these skills can be fostered and cultivated among young learners has already found its way into the agenda of the European educational landscape and has been discussed by politicians and institutions for many years. However, integrating social innovation and entrepreneurship into traditional school curricula has had its difficulties and has not produced the desired results (Eurydice Report 2016). The European Commission proposed years ago a minimum requirement that "all young people should have at least one practical entrepreneurial experience before leaving compulsory school" (EC 2012).

Nowadays, the problem-based and hands-on craft and technical learning, as it is common in makerspaces, has been introduced into Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (=STEAM) education, but rarely in any other curricula. The DOIT learning programme, which presents a different paradigm of maker education, focuses on practice-oriented social innovation and entrepreneurial learning of young people (aged 6-16 years) based on activities in makerspaces. This distinguishes the DOIT programme from makerspace-based STEAM learning, but also from typical Entrepreneurship Education (cf. Geser et al. 2019, p. 4). The fact that formal education and early entrepreneurial education would benefit from principles of "maker education" is not without foundation, but it lacks sufficient empirical data to verify this argument. At this point, the European initiative DOIT- "Entrepreneurial Skills For Young Social Innovators In An Open Digital World" has recently made considerable efforts to analyse the impact on the development of entrepreneurial and social competences, knowledge and skills acquired through this novel way of teaching and training young learners in developing their social innovation project (cf. Unterfrauner et al. 2019, p. 146).

This contribution addresses the effects of the DOIT learning programme, which proposes to support young learners in establishing an entrepreneurial mindset and to develop creative skills for designing social innovation projects. First, we will provide a brief overview of the theoretical background that served as a solid basis for the development of the DOIT learning programme. Then we will describe the workshop activities run with 6 to 16-year-olds in makerspace settings inside and outside school and present two examples of good practice from Austria and Finland. Thirdly, the article presents the results of the scientific evaluation, which show the impact of the trialled DOIT learning programme on specific social and entrepreneurial skills, such as teamwork, self-efficacy and creativity. The contribution closes with a short discussion of the findings, needed adaptations of the programme and future prospects.

2 The DOIT Learning Programme

Based on the predominant discussions in literature and demands in European (education) policy (cf. Lackéus 2015, Eurydice 2016, OECD 2012), the DOIT learning programme builds on and combines three facets: Entrepreneurial education, social innovation process and principles of maker education and digital fabrication tools. Which skills and competences from these areas should be imparted to young learners so that they consider themselves to be social innovators who can actively shape their environment in a creative way? The suggestion is to empower children and youth from six to 16 years to acquire entrepreneurial, social and digital skills and competences using practice-based learning in makerspaces.

The final report of the European Commission's Thematic Working Group on Entrepreneurship Education (2015) defines Entrepreneurship Education "as developing the skills and mind-set that allow people to turn creative ideas into entrepreneurial action" (2015 p.8). It is essential to emphasise that children and young people are not trained as entrepreneurs in the DOIT programme, but are coached in the skills they need to realise and pursue their own ideas and solutions for coping with societal challenges through practice-oriented innovation methods and making tools. In that, the DOIT programme differs from pure entrepreneurship education approaches. The DOIT approach is practice-based ("making") from the onset and provides a learning journey from identifying a local issue, developing a prototype addressing the issue to presenting a prototypic or minimal viable solution in public, to potential users and sponsors. Entrepreneurial questions such as who will adopt the solution (market) and resources required to provide it (costs, financial support) are infused during the making and learning process. This can serve as a pre-stage to learning more about business aspects of entrepreneurial activity. Early entrepreneurship education and maker education (as promoted by DOIT) share a focus on such essential attitudes and competences such as self-confidence, creativity, teamwork, among others (see figure 1). Where early entrepreneurial education is combined with maker activities this also allows fostering design and technical skills, including the productive use of digital tools (cf Geser et al. 2019, p. 4ff).

Figure 1 Competences addressed in the DOIT learning programme – Early Entrepreneurial learning and maker education principles. Sources: Geser et al. (2019, p. 64). The figure refers to competencies highlighted in European Commission et al. 2016 (Figure 3.7); Lindner (2018); Lackéus (2015, p. 13); Schön & Ebner (2017)

The solutions, ideas and prototypes developed in a DOIT innovation workshop are intended to address societal challenges in a creative and novel way. The definition of social innovation to which DOIT refers meets the one promoted by the British innovation foundation NESTA (cited in the Open Book for Social Innovation):

“Our interest is in innovations that are social both in their ends and in their means. Specifically, we define social innovations as new ideas (products, services and models) that simultaneously meet social needs and create new social relationships or collaborations. In other words, they are innovations that are both good for society and enhance society’s capacity to act” (Murray et al., 2010, p. 3).

The development of socially relevant and, if applicable, technology-based prototypes is being encouraged through practice-based and collaborative work in makerspaces and open workshops. A makerspace is equipped with a range of different (digital) fabrication tools and offers space for a variety of creative work for like-minded people. The attitude in a makerspace promotes the sharing of knowledge with others and working collaboratively on projects. It also includes educational activities and focuses on the constructivist way of hands-on learning by doing and tinkering (cf. Geser et al. 2019, p. 61).

The combination of these three facets outlined above offers an approach that focuses on activities in makerspaces with 6 to 16-year-olds to promote the development of social and entrepreneurial skills through practice-oriented social innovation and entrepreneurial learning. DOIT thus differs from typical entrepreneurship education and from makerspace-based STEAM learning. Nevertheless, the goals for the development of certain skills and competences in the field of entrepreneurial thinking and behaviour represent a common ground (cf. Geser et al. 2019, p. 61). In particular, DOIT focuses on social entrepreneurship, supporting children between six and 16 years of age on their way from the idea generation phase with the identification of a challenge from their living environment to the mapping of options for ventures based on their inventions (cf. Schön et al. 2018). These steps following the logic when implementing an innovation project process are called “elements”. They can, but do not have to, be executed one after the other.

The following table presents the seven elements of the DOIT learning programme and indicates the corresponding aspects in the field of social innovation and entrepreneurship as well as the corresponding materials of the DOIT innovation toolbox. The seven elements build upon the above-mentioned facets as well as existing concepts and aims of early entrepreneurial education, social innovation knowhow and maker education (cf. Hornung-Prähauser et al. 2018).

Table 1 Overview of the DOIT learning programme (Details at: www.doit-europe.net/programme)

<i>DOIT learning programme</i>	<i>Social innovation and entrepreneurial aspects</i>	<i>DOIT materials available online (examples)</i>
1. Do it because you can (sensitise)	Awareness of a social problem – Motivation to do something about it – Feeling to be able to work on it	Motivational material (e.g. Crazy Wishes); inspiring success stories
2. Do what matters (explore)	What is the challenge? Where is a need? What can I/we do to make a change? – Collect ideas for potential social innovations	Materials on how to identify social issues and needs (e.g. Social Investigation Board)
3. Do it together (work together)	Build a team – Elaborate and select ideas the team wants to work on	Materials on how to work together and co-create (e.g. Project Canvas)
4. Do it now (create)	First prototyping of ideas – Present, iterate and improve the innovative prototype	Materials on how to prototype (e.g. Hidden Assumptions); present the prototype online
5. Do it better (reflect)	Reflect – Fail forward – Get feedback on the product idea	Materials on how to get valuable feedback (e.g. Reflect on the Process)
6. Do more of it (scale up)	Plan the realisation of the product idea – Develop business plan and marketing material – Find support	Materials on how to develop a first business plan and find support (e.g. Marketing Poster)
7. Do inspire others (share)	Public presentation – Share the story and results of the social innovation project	Materials on how to share (e.g. Project Presentation); present the project story online

Source: Hornung-Prähauser et al. 2018, cited in Geser et al. 2019, p. 66.

New learning resources specific for young learners: The DOIT Innovation Toolbox

One of the main results of the DOIT project initiative is the new innovation toolbox, which provides a handbook, workshop manuals and learning materials supporting each of the seven elements of the DOIT learning programme in a child-friendly manner. The resources can be applied when young learners develop a social innovation project by themselves or are trained by facilitators (e.g. teacher, parents, educators or innovation trainer) in and outside of school and in makerspace settings. The resources were developed, trialled and evaluated during the pilot activities of the partner organisations and are now available under an open license for further usage (accessible free of charge at <https://doit-europe.net/toolbox>). They serve as support in the innovation process and offer both hands-on activities for children and instructions for facilitators, which support the prototyping activities in the open learning environment and the stimulation of innovation skills.

The elaborated DOIT programme, consisting of the seven elements based on existing innovation processes, as well as the innovation material for children and facilitators were tested in the workshop activities of the project. In addition, the effects of the new and open learning setting on the development of creativity and self-efficacy of children and young people were scientifically evaluated.

3 Testing the DOIT Learning Approach: Scope of the Pilot Trainings

During the European DOIT research project, more than 1000 children participated in DOIT activities in 10 European regions (Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Denmark, Finland, Germany, the Netherlands, Slovenia, Spain and Serbia) in two phases (October 2018 to February 2019 and April 2019 to December 2019). The minimum time requirement for an innovation project was fifteen working hours, but the activities and duration of the workshop varied from 2.5 days to 4 months and involved target groups from six to 16 years. The workshops were run in and outside schools, in makerspaces, with mobile makerspaces or pop-up makerspaces. The societal challenges that served as a working basis for the participants in the activities are oriented towards the 17 Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations (cf. UN Development Goals 2020). The DOIT pilot trainings addressed the following themes and sub-themes in the different regions and settings: Living together (e.g. inclusiveness, intercultural living, freedom), education and the future (e.g. school, professional ambitions), health and sport (e.g. physical activity, well-being), participation and rights (e.g. political commitment, privacy, mobility), youth culture and leisure (e.g. games, videos, social media) and environment and nature (e.g. resource efficiency, sustainability, up-cycling and more) (cf. Hollauf & Schön 2020, p. 166).

Part of the careful planning of the DOIT training implementation was also to address the needs of certain specific target groups of children, e.g. in rural areas, children with disabilities, girls (typically underrepresented in makerspaces), and children with advanced making experience (cf. Schön et al., 2019b). The collected experiences serve as recommendations for practitioners on how to reach and work with these target groups. Table 2 gives an overview of the good practice examples.

Table 2 Characteristics of two best practice cases of the DOIT learning programme

	<i>Smart Bicycle Accessories</i>	<i>Sustainable Solution for Social Needs</i>
Organiser & Location	Salzburg Research, Austria	Lappeenranta University, Finland
Short Description	Students developed bicycle accessories using the material “Smart Cardboard Prototype” to encourage more people to use the bicycle. With the help of experts, they also thought about the feasibility and the target group of their product. They presented the final solutions in a public presentation.	Students developed solutions and prototypes to self-identified social problems. They applied entrepreneurial skills and creativity, learned to formulate and to pitch business ideas. The students presented the results to a entrepreneurs’ committee and pitched them to the audience in a final presentation.
Time frame	October 2019, two half-days	November to December 2019, six three-hour sessions
Number of participants, Age	21 students from 14 to 16 years	45 students from 12 to 14 years
Subtopic	Fitness and Health	Environment & Nature
Challenge	How can we motivate people to increase their use of bicycles with the help of a bicycle accessory?	How can we use nature driven innovation to address sustainability and societal challenges?
Setting	The workshop took place as part of a regular school activity at a secondary school. For this purpose, the facilitators installed a mobile makerspace in the school’s basement.	Two workshops parts took place in the school, whereas three sequences were conducted at the university campus. One unit consisted of the visit of a forest trail.

Source: Podmetina D., Lappeenranta University of Technology (2020)

Good Practice Workshop 1 - Smart Bicycle Accessories

The *Smart Bicycle Accessories* workshop took place in October 2019 in a federal commercial academy in Hallein, a medium-sized city in the county of Salzburg, Austria. The 21 students were 14 to 16 years old and formed the first class of the "Industrial Business" training, which focuses strongly on the promotion of entrepreneurial skills. In a preparatory co-creation workshop, the students and school’s facilitators turned the general theme „Health & Fitness" themselves into a workshop topic relevant for them personally: "Ideas for Climate Action for the region Tennengau - Smart Accessories for Attractive Bicycle Mobility". For this theme, solutions were to be developed and designed with the support material “Smart Cardboard Prototype”. The challenge for which the students were asked to find a (digital) solution was then summarised as: *"How can we motivate people to increase their use of bicycles with the help of a bicycle*

accessory?” The accessories should be designed using the “Smart Cardboard Prototype” which provides the possibility to equip the first prototype (e.g. cardboard prototype) with planned sensor functions without the need for real electronics and sensors. It is intended to provide initial information as to whether the planned function is possible or not and can thus help in the further implementation of the idea, for example in the calculation of the manufacturing price or needed support from different stakeholders.

The work schedule encompassed two consecutive days, six hours each (Co-design and Pre-Test and hands-on working phase), followed by a public final presentation and feedback session, which took place two weeks after the workshop days. In the workshop series, there was only a broad time schedule, marked by the introduction of new methods or steps for the work process and interim presentation of the results by the groups. Here a clear improvement in time management by the students was evident and the tools presented, such as the DOIT Business Model Canvas, were also taken into account in the considerations of the prototypes. External mobility experts and entrepreneurs (owner of bike shop and producer) were invited to the working process and to the final presentation. Their role was to provide feedback on the ideas and suggestions for improvement on the prototypes and offering support in building the prototypes and implementation. The presence of the experts from the field of bicycle mobility additionally inspired the students and made them very proud to see their ideas appreciated by experienced entrepreneurs.

In summary, this best practice workshop aimed to develop among young learners an awareness of the social need for innovative sustainable transport and personal mobility, design and creativity prototyping skills for new functionalities of a familiar product (bicycle), self-esteem and presentation skills for innovations.

Good Practice Workshop 2: “Sustainable Solution for Social Needs”

These series of workshops implemented by Lappeenranta University were dedicated to the problems and solutions in the field of social entrepreneurship and innovation, sustainability, environment and nature. Students learned to identify environmental and societal problems in the neighbourhood and globally, and approach them using a broad set of tools, guided by facilitators. The awareness of environmental and social problems was raised, and children were empowered to come up with their own solutions. In total, 45 students from 7th grade (age 12-13, 22 students) and 8th grade (age 13-14, 23 students) from a local school participated in the workshops. Students were introduced to social entrepreneurship, innovation, sustainability, biomimetic (the imitation of natural phenomena in technical innovations). They identified societal problems themselves and developed solutions and prototypes while participating in the five days workshops at the LUT University. Students developed prototypes, learned to formulate and to pitch business ideas, and analyse the market. In the end, students presented the prototypes, videos and presentations to the entrepreneurs’ committee and pitched them to the audience.

The workshop aimed not only to train children how to identify and solve societal problems in a creative and entrepreneurial way, but to encourage them to do it collaboratively, formulate, and pitch their ideas eloquently. Various activities promoted the development of social and entrepreneurial skills: The students gained an insight into nature driven innovation and engineering before they participated in creativity workshops to identify problems relevant to them and worked collaboratively on prototypes and solutions. The introduction to agile project management supported the work in teams and additional workshop sequences on environmental sensing and data sculpturing helped the students in the further prototyping process and fostered their data literacy skills. During the final presentations, experts gave feedback on the results.

These two best practice DOIT workshop examples, which were supported personally by the authors, give an insight into the different topics, settings and possibilities of innovation workshops, as they are proposed by the DOIT learning programme. The overall aim is to raise awareness of tackling societal issues, train an entrepreneurial mind-set among children and youth as well as to foster their creativity and self-efficacy. Following the DOIT learning programme, Salzburg Research and Lappeenranta University have designed the workshops along the steps from problem identification, ideation and creativity to developing the first prototype, pitching and collecting feedback, improving and developing the second prototype and presenting it to the public. The presentation of the prototype examples fostered the acquisition of technical competences in each element of the learning programme using e.g. simple electronics like LEDs, 2D and 3D designs and simple coding techniques. Moreover, exploring systematically people's needs and the ideation process transferred social innovation skills and encouraged the students to tackle societal problems. This is furthermore supported by the collaborative team work focusing on delivering a tangible prototype and considering that the product can be implemented. Additionally, the introduction to presentation techniques and the constructive feedback from the experts further enhanced the students' self-confidence. Throughout the whole process it was very important to maintain the students' motivation in case of barriers and to perceive these as guiding aspects of the process. Through the independent work, combined with the facilitators' guiding, the students were able to experience the necessary competences already mentioned and to adopt them for future projects.

In the next section, the general parameters and basics for scientific research and the main findings on the effects of the open learning settings for the acquisition of skill and competences will be outlined. It is followed by a collection of recommendations for practitioners, extracted from the experiences made in the workshops.

4 Effects of the innovation workshops using the DOIT learning programme on social and entrepreneurial skill development

Based on Lackéus' (2015, p. 13) model on entrepreneurship education and co-evaluation approach with practice partners the following evaluation dimensions on a participant level were selected as being indicative for entrepreneurial skills and attitudes: creativity, self-efficacy, teamwork and collaboration skills, dealing with uncertainty, perseverance, empathy and knowing others' needs, motivation and sense of initiative and planning and management skills. While the first two dimensions were assessed quantitatively, the remaining dimensions were addressed qualitatively with facilitator interviews, workshop documentation, and collecting children's feedback.

For measuring creativity, the "Test for Creative Thinking-Drawing Production" (TCT-DP; in German: TDS-Z, Urban & Jellen, 2010) was chosen as being suitable for DOIT as it is a language free test, which can easily be used in different countries and also for the age range. It further provides for so-called parallel versions: a Form A for the pre-test, and a form B for the post-test. As for measuring self-efficacy there was no published questionnaire available that was suitable for the quite large age range, we constructed a survey that is based on published scales with adaptations on item level (Boyd & Vozikis, 1994; Deusinger, 1986; Krampen, 1991; Midgley et al., 2000). The survey was translated into different national languages. In filling in the questionnaire, younger children were assisted by facilitators, while children from eight years would autonomously fill in the survey. Our statistical analysis shows significant effects of the DOIT action in both, in terms of creativity and self-efficacy with moderate effect sizes of 0.243 and 0.207 for the overall group of participating children.

Interestingly in contrast to the assumption that creativity would correlate with age, the younger age group (6-10 years) showed the same level of creativity as the older age group (11-16 years) in the pre-test. In the post-test, both age groups gained significantly higher creativity scores, although the older age group obviously benefited more from the DOIT action in terms of creativity. Both age groups show about the same level of self-efficacy at the beginning of the DOIT action but younger ones tend to have higher scores afterward. Thus, in contrast to creativity where the older ones gained higher scores in the post-test, it is the younger ones who outscore the older ones in the self-efficacy survey. In order to prove that the score gain in the creativity test and the self-efficacy survey can be attributed to the DOIT action and not to other confounding variables (Bortz & Döring, 2013), we have created a "quasi" control group within our data set with children who did not fulfill the minimum requirement of attending at least 15 hours of the programme. When we compare the creativity test of these two groups (an experiential group with at least 15 hours attended and a control group with fewer hours) then we see that the experimental group increased their score significantly while the control group did not. The same applies to the self-efficacy survey.

In relation to teamwork, collaboration, plan, and management skills, the interviewed facilitators noted increasing competences in all of these areas; interestingly some groups established task and responsibility division within the group, while others worked on all tasks collaboratively. Younger children needed some more support in planning all the tasks needed towards the final prototype but in general, as noted by the facilitators, groups worked quite autonomously in many cases. Failing and dealing with uncertainties was part of the design process. This open learning approach, in the beginning, was challenging for some children as facilitators noted as it took some time for facilitators to communicate that failing was regarded as an opportunity to learn. In terms of motivation and perseverance, it was important that children developed a sense of ownership- from the ideation to the realization of the prototype and sharing it towards the end of the DOIT program.

5 Recommendations for Practice

Based on the experience gained by the facilitators in the workshop activities and the results of the accompanying scientific research, the facilitating guidelines for practitioners were worked out (see table 3 below). Inexperienced teachers, in particular, find it difficult to integrate project-based learning along the steps of a social innovation process and the related open learning environment into traditional class settings or curricula. Nevertheless, the recommendations and workshop guidelines can be applied in any thematic learning setting fostering social innovation and are aimed at all type of educators, youth workers and parents. They offer practical and didactical approaches for facilitators to plan and conduct their own workshops and thus support children and young people in developing social and entrepreneurial skills. The “Key Requirements, Settings and Processes for a Successful DOIT Action” capture lessons learnt in the workshop activities and provide guidelines on how to engage the participants in the DOIT facets. The following table highlights the most important recommendations on how to foster the acquisition of social, entrepreneurial and digital competences in an open learning environment (see Vloet et al., 2020).

Table 3 Recommendations for a successful activity fostering social innovation projects with young learners

	<i>Social Innovation</i>	<i>Entrepreneurial Learning</i>	<i>Digital Fabrication</i>
Motivate	Make societal issues tangible and relatable – use problems from immediate environment	Set a creative and safe setting – communicate that mistakes are crucial part of the process	Spark motivation through simple hands-on activities – start with small tasks
Open process	Ask open design questions – a problem does not have one simple solution	Support the learners to do as much as possible themselves – needs individual guidance	Freedom of exploration of technology – choose material that needs minimal guidance
Open outcomes	Social innovation is a iterative process – critical reflection of outcomes is desired	Focus on learning outcomes of the process, not the prototypes – focus on individual growth of skills	Positive outcomes are crucial and differ per child

Source: Hollauf E., abbreviated version of original source in Vloet 2020

In addition, a multilingual DOIT Handbook & Workshop Manual contains detailed descriptions of the seven elements (Sensitize, Explore, Collaborate, Create, Reflect, Scale-up, Share) of the DOIT learning program. The handbook addresses the relevance of the elements along the steps of a social innovation project, gives examples from the workshop sequences carried out and highlights materials from the online innovation toolbox that can be applied. These materials should enable interested practitioners to plan and accompany innovation processes. Besides defining their own challenges, users can also choose from a collection of workshop descriptions.

6 Discussion and Outlook

The results show significant benefits for the young participants in terms of creativity and self-efficacy, which are prerequisites for developing their own ideas and establishing belief in pursuing them. The evaluation design has followed a pre-post comparison of the scores, comparing the scores before and after taking part in DOIT workshops. Thus, the analysis cannot anticipate any long-term changes within the students. However, we can conclude that making approaches followed by DOIT workshops with young children can contribute to some extent to the development of entrepreneurial skills and attitudes. Although these open learning settings particularly challenge students as well as facilitators, these types of learning settings adapt well to the next generations' challenges of creativity and problem-solving attributes for social innovation development. Based on

the experiences and evaluation results, it was also possible to define recommendations for future educational practice.. Young learners should be granted the opportunity and infrastructure to acquire an entrepreneurial mind-set and skills that enable them to actively shape their environment and to implement their ideas in a sustainable way.

Besides developing the DOIT learning programme for children and young people, training also the facilitator has become a crucial aspect of the project. The practice partners are currently in the roll-out phase, in which these training will be carried out, with the goal of training 1000 people to become DOIT facilitators, who will then be able to design and conduct social innovation workshops according to the DOIT learning program, with their students and pupils. In addition, the main outcomes, methods and tools will be presented in the form of a train-the-trainer Online Course and made available to interested learners (Details at: <https://doit-europe.net/online-course>). The innovation toolbox offers interested practitioners material and methods to design and conduct innovation workshops themselves, as the material is open-licensed. It is therefore available for transfer and local adaptation into national educational initiatives.

Acknowledgment

The DOIT project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 770063. The content of this publication does not reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Responsibility for the information and views expressed in the publication lies entirely with the authors. URL: www.doit-europe.net

7 References and Notes

Boyd, N. G., & Vozikis, G. S. (1994). The Influence of Self-Efficacy on the Development of Entrepreneurial Intentions and Actions. In J. Kuhl & J. Beckmann (Eds.), *From cognition to behavior* (pp. 11–39). Springer. <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/104225879401800404>

Deusinger, I. M. (1986). *Die Frankfurter Selbstkonzeptskalen:(FSKN)*. Hogrefe, Verlag für Psychologie.

Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions (2012). Rethinking Education: Investing in skills for better socio-economic outcomes, COM(2012) 669 final, Strasbourg. URL: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52012DC0669> [accessed April 26, 2020]

Eurydice (2016). *Entrepreneurship Education at School in Europe*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Retrieved from <http://doi.org/10.2797/301610> [accessed April 26, 2020]

European Commission's Thematic Working Group on Entrepreneurship Education (2015). Thematic Working Group on Entrepreneurship Education. Final Report-Prepared in November 2014. Published in URL: <https://www.tesguide.eu/policy-strategy/itemid/40911/> [accessed April 25, 2020]

European Commission's Thematic Working Group on Entrepreneurship Education (2014). Thematic Working Group on Entrepreneurship Education Final Report. URL: https://ec.europa.eu/assets/eac/education/experts-groups/2011-2013/key/entrepreneurship-report-2014_en.pdf [accessed May 5, 2020]

Geser, G., Hollauf, E., Hornung-Prähauser, V., Schön, S., Vloet, F. (2019). Makerspaces as Social Innovation and Entrepreneurship Education Environments: The DOIT Learning Program. In: *Discourse and Communication for Sustainable Education*, 2019, 2, pp. 60-71. Open Access: <https://content.sciendo.com/view/journals/dcse/10/2/article-p60.xml> [accessed May 5th 2020]

Hollauf, E. & Schön, S. (2019). Gemeinsam die Welt verbessern - soziale Innovationen und Maker Education: Ausgewählte Projekte und Erfahrungen. [Improving the World Together - Social Innovation and Maker Education: Selected Projects and Experiences] In: S. Ingold, B. Maurer & D. Trüby (Hrsg.): *Chance MakerSpace - Making trifft Schule*. [Chance Makerspace - Making Meets School.] München: kopaed 2019, pp. 119-135.

Hollauf, E. & Schön, S. (i.p., 2020). Pop-Up-Makerspaces an Schulen. Erfahrungen aus der europäischen Initiative DOIT. [Pop-Up-Makerspaces in Schools. Experiences from the European Initiative DOIT] In: Heinzl, V., Seidl, T., Stang, R. (Eds.). *Lernwelt Makerspace. Perspektiven im öffentlichen und wissenschaftlichen Kontext*. [Learning World Makerspace. Perspectives in Public and Scientific Context.] De Gruyter Saur, Berlin, pp. 166-176.

Hornung-Prähauser, V., Schön, S., Teplov, R., Podmetina, D. (2018): Social Innovation Training in Makerspaces with the new DOIT approach. In: *Proceedings of the ISPIM conference 2018 in Stockholm*, Manchester: The International Society for Professional Innovation Management (ISPIM), 1–15.

Krampen, G. (1991). *FKK Fragebogen zu Kompetenz-und Kontrollüberzeugungen*. Göttingen: Hogrefe.

Lackéus, Martin (2015). *Entrepreneurship in education. What, Why, When, How*. OECD/EC. URL: https://www.oecd.org/cfe/leed/BGP_Entrepreneurship-in-Education.pdf [accessed April 25, 2020]

- Lindner, J. (2018). Entrepreneurship education for a sustainable future. *Discourse and Communication for Sustainable Education*, 9(1), 115–127. Retrieved from <http://doi.org/10.2478/dcse-2018-0009> [accessed May 5, 2020]
- Makhlouf, H.H., (2011). Social entrepreneurship: generating solutions to global challenges. *International Journal of Management & Information Systems (IJMIS)*, 15(1).
- Midgley, C., Maehr, M. L., Hruda, L. Z., Anderman, E., Anderman, L., Freeman, K. E., & Urdan, T. (2000). Manual for the patterns of adaptive learning scales. *Ann Arbor, 1001*, 48109–1259.
- Murray, R., Caulier-Grice, J., & Mulgan, G. (2010). The open book of social Innovation. London: The Young Foundation & NESTA. Retrieved from <https://youngfoundation.org/publications/the-open-book-of-social-innovation> [accessed April 25, 2020]
- OECD (2012). Gender Equality in Education, Employment and Entrepreneurship. Final Report to the MCM. URL: <https://www.oecd.org/employment/50423364.pdf> [accessed April 25, 2020]
- Schön, S., & Ebner, M. (2017). Maker-Bewegung macht Schule: Hintergründe, Beispiele sowie erste Erfahrungen [Maker movement makes school: background, examples and first experiences]. In Erpenbeck J., & Sauter, W. (Eds.). *Handbuch Kompetenzentwicklung im Netz* [Handbook Competence Development in the Internet]. Stuttgart: Schäffer-Poeschel Verlag, 257-270.
- Schön, S., Friebe, L., Hollauf, E., Rosenova, M. (2019b). Report on issues to reach special requirements for special target groups and settings. Deliverable 2.5 of the Horizon 2020 project DOIT, EC grant agreement no 770063, Salzburg, Austria: Salzburg Research
- Unterfrauner, E., Voigt, C., Schön, S. (2019). Towards a Model of Early Entrepreneurial Education: Appreciation, Facilitation and Evaluation. In Di Mascio, T., Vittorini, P., Gennari, R., De la Prieta, F., Rodríguez, S., Temperini, M., Azambuja Silveira, R., Popescu, E., Lancia, L. (Eds.), *Methodologies and Intelligent Systems for Technology Enhanced Learning*, 8th International Conference (pp. 139-146), retrieval date, from <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007%2F978-3-319-98872-6>
- Urban, K. K., & Jellen, H. G. (2010). Test zum Schöpferischen Denken - Zeichnerisch: (TSD-Z). Pearson Assessment & Information GmbH.
- Vloet, Frank (2020). Key requirements, settings, processes of a successful DOIT action (4.4) of the Horizon 2020 project DOIT, EC grant agreement no 770063, Salzburg, Austria: Salzburg Research.